

MARKETING INNOVATION, MARKET FOCUS, BUILDING CONFIDENCE TO CONSUMERS AND THE QUALITY OF PRODUCTS THAT AFFECT THE SUCCESS OF THE BUSINESS OF FURNITURE MANUFACTURERS, EXPORTERS OF THAILAND

PANWIPA SUPATANAPAT¹, BUNDIT PUNGNIRUND², NATTAPONG TECHARATTANASED³, PLUEMCHAI SIN-AKORN⁴ and JIRAPHORN SAWASDIRUK⁵

^{1, 2, 3, 4, 5} Suan Sunandha Rajabhat University, Thailand.

E-Mail: s61484945028@ssru.ac.th¹, bundit.pu@ssru.ac.th², nattapong.te@ssru.ac.th³, pleumjai.si@ssru.ac.th⁴, jiraphorn.sa@ssru.ac.th⁵

Abstract

Encouraging entrepreneurs in Thailand's furniture exports is a response to the market trends in the global furniture business. Thailand's top five furniture export destinations are the United States, Japan, China, Malaysia and Vietnam. The exports to these countries have been continuously conducted during the recent periods of time. At present, the situation of the COVID-19 pandemic has caused furniture exporters in Thailand to face many problems, as well as lack of competitiveness at both regional and global levels where there has a greater number of competitors. The furniture export business is therefore inefficient. The objectives of this research were to: 1) study levels of marketing innovations, market focus, establishment of consumer confidence, product quality, and the success in the operation of the Thai furniture exporters; 2) examine influences of marketing innovations, market focus, establishment of consumer confidence, and product quality on the success in the operation of the Thai furniture exporters; and 3) develop a model for the success in the operation of the Thai furniture exporters. This research employed a mixed research methodology combining quantitative and qualitative methods. For the quantitative research part, the research sample consisted of 380 Thai furniture exporters. The sample size was determined based on the criterion of 20 times the observed variables. They were selected via stratified sampling. Data were collected with the use of a questionnaire and analyzed with a structural equation model. As for the qualitative research component, in-depth interviews were conducted with 20 key informants including executives and experts in Thai furniture export business. The findings showed that: 1) product quality, establishment of consumer confidence, market focus, marketing innovations, and the success in the operation of Thai furniture exporters were rated at a high level; 2) product quality, establishment of consumer confidence, marketing innovations, and market focus had an influence on success in the operation of the Thai furniture exporters, with a .05 level of statistical significance; and 3) the model for the success in the operation of the Thai furniture exporters, developed by the researcher, was called QCIFS Model, consisting of Q (referring to product quality), C (referring to building consumer confidence), I (referring to marketing innovations), F (referring to market focus), and S (referring to success in the operation of Thai furniture exporters). In addition, the qualitative research findings also revealed that in creating the success in the operation of the Thai furniture exporters, the entrepreneurs should study both formal and informal customer requirements in each country, synthesize the findings, and use them to design the products to meet with the needs of the majority of customers in the countries which were the export destinations. These research findings can be applied as the guidelines in formulating a policy to support the operation of the Thai furniture exporters. Quality of the products should be used to build consumers' confidence by utilizing marketing innovations and market focus which serve as the pull factors in the consumers'

purchasing decisions. Besides, marketing competitiveness of the Thai furniture export business can also be developed through the quality of products and services.

Keywords: Marketing Innovations/ Market Focus/ Establishment of Consumer Confidence/ Product Quality/ Success in the Operation/Furniture Exporters

1. Introduction

Similar with other industries, furniture industry is an important industry which have global importance (Abu, Gholami, Saman, Zakuan, & Streimikiene, 2019). It has major contribution globally to several economies. In most of the countries, furniture industry has key importance due to several benefits related to the local as well as national development. This industry generating revenue which has contribution to the global economic development. It also provides several opportunities for the people to generate income. Therefore, the importance of this industry cannot be neglected along with the other industries.

Along with the other nations, the furniture industry of Thailand is also an important industry (Rakkarn & Dersing, 2018; Sritong, 2021) because it has importance for Thailand through different dimensions. This industry contributing to the national development through different ways. For instance, the revenue generated from this industry has contribution to the gross domestic product (GDP) of Thailand. In this way, this industry has influence on the economic development of Thailand. The increase or decrease in the performance of this industry has direct influence on the economic development of Thailand. This industry is also important because it is providing several job opportunities for the people. The development of community is in various areas of Thailand are dependent on the furniture industry. The Thai furniture industry employs a workforce of 400,000, of these 165,000 are employed by businesses with higher than 10 workers. Furniture in wood is projected to account for 70% of all the furniture formed and the material most frequently used in furniture production is parawood (60%). Thailand is rich of various valuable trees which are used in furniture. The importance of this industry can be observed with the help of Figure 1.

Figure 1: Domestic sales volume of wooden furniture in Thailand from 3rd quarter 2019 to 3rd quarter 2021

However, with the increase in the cases of COVID-19, the performance of this industry has decreased (Ratnasingam et al., 2020). In the years of COVID-19, the exports of Thailand declined significantly. Due to the decrease in exports the performance of the industry decreased along with the performance of exporters. The low performance of exporters in furniture industry causes to decrease the overall performance and its loss the market shares internationally. These industries significantly affected along with the other industries. After the end of COVID-19, it is needed to reestablish the market furniture product exports. In this way, promotion of exporter's performance is most important which is needed to ensure with the help of various strategies. Although all the industries affected globally, however, furniture industry of Thailand faced major consequences.

In this way, the current study is an attempt to promote exporters performance in Thailand furniture industry. According to the current study, number of factors can influence the exporter performance (Filatotchev, Liu, Buck, & Wright, 2009) and it is needed to identify the factors for the better performance of the industry. The study proposed that exporter's performance can be promoted with the help of the establishment of consumer confidence. Due to COVID-19 disturbance (González & Pérez-Uribe, 2021), the consumer confidence is declined which required to reestablish. Furthermore, market focus as well as product quality is most important to address in various products. Additionally, marketing is needed to promote different products and innovation in marketing activities has major importance. Therefore, the establishment of consumer confidence, market focus, product quality and marketing innovation has the potential to promote exporter performance. In this way, this study proposed following objectives; 1) to study levels of marketing innovations, market focus, establishment of consumer confidence, product quality, and the success in the operation of the Thai furniture exporters; 2) to examine the influences of marketing innovations, market focus, establishment of consumer confidence, and product quality on the success in the operation of the Thai furniture exporters; and 3) develop a model for the success in the operation of the Thai furniture exporters. The objectives of the current study are established by focusing on various literature gaps in the field of furniture industry. Literature neglected various areas in the furniture industry, for instance, the exporters performance is ignored by the previous studies. Additionally, this study considered the establishment of consumer confidence which is not addressed in other studies. All the new elements investigated in the study has major importance for the literature. These elements are also most important for the practical implications which can lead to increase the furniture industry performance in Thailand.

2. Literature Review

Export performance is the relative success or failure of the efforts of an organization or nation to sell domestically-produced goods as well as services in other nations. Generally, the export performance is based on the exporter success. All the companies working in a country are the exporter of various goods and services and their performance collectively shape the export performance of the country. Therefore, the exporter performance and export performance of furniture industry are consistent. This study is focusing on the exporter performance along with different other factors. The exporter performance in the furniture industry is considered in

relation to the establishment of the consumer confidence, market focus, product innovation and marketing innovation. This element has major influence on exporter success which define the exporter performance or export performance of the country. Based on these factors, the current study proposed a framework for exporter success in Thai furniture industry. Finally, the framework of the study in Figure 2 shows the relationship between establishment of consumer confidence, market focus, product quality, marketing innovation and exporter success.

Figure 2: Study Framework

The confidence of the consumer (Maheswari & Hidayat, 2021) towards the various exporters is most important. The level of trust must be developed between the exporter as well as consumer (Macready et al., 2020). The satisfactory trust between two parties leads to the higher level of confidence which causes to lead various transactions in terms of exports and imports. Similarly in the furniture industry, due to the disturbance of COVID-19, the confidence of the consumer declined in relation to the Thai furniture industry. The reestablishment of the confidence has effect on marketing innovation strategies. Positive level of confidence among the consumer can lead to the marketing innovation practices. It also has significant relation with the exporter success. Because higher level of consumer confidence led to purchase products and services from the exporter. Therefore, the study proposed the positive effect of development of consumer confidence on marketing innovation and exporter success.

H1. Establishment of consumer confidence has positive effect on marketing innovation.

H2. Establishment of consumer confidence has positive effect on exporter success.

The furniture industry of Thailand loses the market share internationally due to the COVID-19. Therefore, it is important for the furniture industry of Thailand to capture the market share again. In this direction, it is important for this industry to focus on the market and capture various opportunities for the export. As reported in previous studies that market focus has central importance in any business activity (Mathafena & Msimango-Galawe, 2022; Sampaio, Hernández-Mogollón, & Rodrigues, 2018). With the increase in business operations in the market the competition is increasing globally, therefore, to capture the market share is one of the challenges for the companies. In this direction, the focus on the market is most important to establish in relation with the customers. Therefore, it is important to market the products with the help of market focus. (Kerdpitak, 2022a) The Thai furniture industry can export the

products after capturing the market with the help of marketing innovation. In this way, the focus on the market can provide various opportunities for marketing innovation. Thus, this study proposed a relationship between market focus and marketing innovation.

H3. Market focus has positive effect on marketing innovation.

Product quality is always important in business activities because the customers always require high quality products (Cappelli & Cini, 2021; Dreyfus, Psarommatis, May, & Kiritsis, 2022). Similarly in the furniture market of Thailand the high product quality is required, particularly, in the exports of various goods and services the product quality must be high to capture the customers. As in the comparative business environment, all businesses are providing significant level of quality, however, the customer prefer the higher quality. Therefore, to get success in the business activities the higher quality products are important (González-Arias et al., 2022; Liu et al., 2022). Product quality also has relationship with marketing innovation. The marketing innovation activities can be promoted with the help of fire product quality. However, the low product quality may decrease the marketing innovation activities among the business industry. Furthermore, this study also highlighted that the quality has influence on exporter success. As reported in previous studies that export success or export performance is based on the quality of the products (Moghaddam et al., 2011; Kerdpitak, 2022). Thus, quality has influence on marketing innovation as well as exporter success.

H4. Product quality has positive effect on marketing innovation.

H5. Product quality has positive effect on exporter success.

Finally, this study also proposed the relationship between marketing innovation and exporter success. Marketing activities always influence on business activities (Purba, Simanjutak, Malau, Sholihat, & Ahmadi, 2021). Similarly, marketing innovation activities in the furniture market can promote the exporter success. It has major relationship with export performance through marketing innovation which provide the awareness among the people to purchase a specific product along with the specific features. Furthermore, along with the direct effects, the current study also considered the indirect effect of marketing innovation.

H6. Marketing innovation has positive effect on exporter success.

H7. Marketing innovation mediates the relationship between establishment of consumer confidence and exporter success.

H8. Marketing innovation mediates the relationship between market focus and exporter success.

H9. Marketing innovation mediates the relationship between product quality and exporter success.

3. Methodology

This study established a relationship between establishment of consumer confidence, market focus, product quality, marketing innovation and exporter success. This relationship is measured with the help of two ways. First, this relationship is measured with the help of

questionnaire. Therefore, while using qualitative research, this study employed cross-sectional research design in which a survey questionnaire is used. The questionnaire is developed with the help of adapting scale items from previous studies. Questionnaire is developed by using scale items of five variables; establishment of consumer confidence, market focus, product quality, marketing innovation and exporter success. Establishment of consumer confidence is made by considering various activities to increase the level of confidence by the consumer. As due to the COVID-19, the disturbance in business transactions decreased the consumer confidence. Furthermore, market focus is considered by considering various opportunities in the market to export furniture products. It is majorly based on to capture the international market for exports. Marketing innovation is considered by considering scale items related to the new innovation as well as technology in marketing practices to promote various products. Exporter success is considered with the help of considering the contracts of the exporters and its level of success as well as failure. Second, this study employed qualitative research approach in which the interviews are used for data collection.

Therefore, this research employed a mixed research methodology combining. While using mixed method, quantitative and qualitative methods are used in this study. For the quantitative research part, the research sample consisted of 380 Thai furniture exporters was considered. The sample size was determined based on the criterion of 20 times the observed variables. Respondents were selected via stratified sampling. Stratified random sampling is a technique of sampling that includes the partition of the whole population into smaller sub-groups which are known as strata. Therefore, the current study also divided the population and developed various strata. In stratified random sampling, the strata are formed grounded on members' common qualities or characteristics such as income or educational achievement.

Data were collected with the use of a questionnaire and analyzed with a structural equation modeling (SEM). Additionally, Likert scale is used in this study to collect the opinion and views of the respondents (Krzych, Lach, Joniec, Cisowski, & Bochenek, 2018). As for the qualitative research component, in-depth interviews were conducted with 20 key informants including executives and experts in Thai furniture export business.

4. Results

This study analyzed the 380 responses to examine the relationship among variables. Before to test the relationship, this study carried out data analysis to fix the errors in the data. This is study observed various errors such as missing value, outlier in the data and normality of the data. In this process, it is observed that exporter success has five missing values, innovation has three missing values and market focus has six missing values. All the missing values are treated by using the methods available in the literature. Two outliers are found in exporter success, three outliers are observed in establishment of consumer confidence which were treated with the help of recommended methods. Finally, data statistics are given in Table 1.

Table 1: Statistical test of empirical variables (n=380)

Variable	M	S.D.	%CV	Sk	Ku	χ^2	P-value
cmcf	3.94	0.79	20.05	-1.604	-2.240	7.590	.022
fise	4.14	0.71	17.15	-2.343	-.865	6.239	.044
inst	4.29	0.70	16.32	-3.453	-2.044	16.099	.000
dimk	4.03	0.85	21.09	-2.672	-3.409	18.757	.000
onli	4.09	0.77	18.83	-2.415	-2.934	14.442	.001
mkup	4.10	0.74	18.05	-2.225	-2.503	11.213	.004
func	4.23	0.72	17.02	-3.012	-1.744	12.114	.002
mode	4.26	0.72	16.90	-3.312	-2.425	16.848	.000
effe	4.09	0.760	18.58	-2.216	-1.152	6.239	.044
stou	4.23	0.69	16.31	-2.791	-1.825	11.123	.004
cure	3.99	0.85	21.30	-2.324	-2.323	1.796	.005
sedi	4.08	0.85	20.83	-3.080	-3.156	19.450	.000
mone	4.26	0.70	16.43	-3.172	-2.206	14.929	.001
cust	4.38	0.70	15.98	-4.302	-2.004	22.525	.000
inte	4.25	0.76	17.88	-3.538	-1.906	16.150	.000
grow	4.21	0.71	16.75	-3.080	-2.632	16.412	.000
orde	4.20	0.75	17.69	-3.471	-2.404	17.824	.000
expo	4.18	0.74	17.70	-2.878	-2.643	15.272	.000
expa	4.24	0.71	16.75	-3.021	-2.162	13.802	.001

There are number of techniques available in the literature to analyze the data. However, by reviewing the literature this study selected the most suitable data analysis technique. The data analysis technique used in the study is structural equation modelling which is highlighted in the literature as an important technique to examine the relationship between variables with the help of primary data (Mustafa, Nordin, & Razzaq, 2020; Purwanto, Asbari, Santoso, Paramarta, & Sunarsi, 2020; Rahi & Abd Ghani, 2018). First of all, this technique is used to examine the reliability as well as validity. First part of analysis confirmed factor analysis which is carried out and the results are given in Table 2. Result shows that internal item reliability is considered with the help of examining the factor loadings and results show that none of the factor loading is below 0.5 which is minimum threshold level in the current study. Therefore, all the scale items are retained and none of the scale item is deleted. Furthermore, internal item reliability is not sufficient the current study also considered the Cronbach Alpha which is higher than 0.7 for all the variables. Finally, the convergent validity is considered with the help of composite reliability and average variance extracted. The composite reliability for all the variables has above 0.7 and average variance expected which is above 0.5. The achievement of these values confirmed the convergent validity in the study. Additionally, it is also confirmed the discriminant validity (Hyland, Karatzias, Shevlin, & Cloitre, 2019) with the help of average variance extracted square root. Factor loadings are given in Table 2.

Table 2: Factor Loadings. (n = 380)

Variable	Factor Loading (λ)	Error (θ)	t	R ²
Establishment of consumer confidence (BLCFD)				
cmcf	.51	.24	8.63	.76
fise	.85	.28	12.00	.72
inst	.59	.25	9.64	.75
$\rho_c = .83 \rho_v = .63$				
Market focus (MKFOC)				
dimk	.73	.47	14.52	.53
onli	.88	.22	17.65	.78
mkup	.65	.57	12.99	.43
$\rho_c = .80 \rho_v = .57$				
Product quality (PDQUA)				
func	.69	.52	10.21	.48
mode	.69	.53	12.79	.47
effe	.77	.41	14.18	.59
stou	.67	.45	12.52	.55
$\rho_c = .81 \rho_v = .51$				
Marketing innovations (MKINO)				
cure	.96	.07	25.96	.93
sedi	.48	.77	9.76	.23
$\rho_c = .71 \rho_v = .57$				
Exporters Success (EXPFU)				
mone	.78	.47	8.81	.53
cust	.76	.49	8.58	.51
inte	.59	.45	10.11	.55
grow	.74	.41	10.16	.59
orde	.76	.42	14.01	.58
expo	.62	.42	11.62	.58
expa	.59	.46	10.95	.54
$\rho_c = .88 \rho_v = .52$				

Note: Establishment of consumer confidence=BLCFD; Market focus =MKFOC; Product quality =PDQUA; Marketing innovations=MKINO; Exporters Success=EXPFU

Finally, in the second part of the data analysis this study examined the relationship between variables. T-value and beta value are considered to check the status of the hypotheses (Cheah, Sarstedt, Ringle, Ramayah, & Ting, 2018; Sarstedt, Hair Jr, Nitzl, Ringle, & Howard, 2020). The effect of establishment of the consumer confidence is considered in relation to the marketing innovation and exporter success. It is found that establishment of consumer confidence has significant effect on marketing innovation. It also has significant effect on export success. Furthermore, the effect of market focus is considered on marketing innovation.

This relationship is also significant and positive. Moreover, the role of product innovation is considered in relation to the marketing innovation and export success. It is identified that product innovation has significant relationship with marketing innovation. Product innovation also has significant relationship with exporter success. In direct effect, it is also found that marketing innovation has significant effect on exporter success. Therefore, the hypothesis 1, hypothesis 2, hypothesis 3, hypothesis 4. Hypothesis 5 and hypothesis 6 are significant. The model of the study with results is given in Figure 3 and results are reported in Table 3.

Table 3: Parameter estimation result of direct effect coefficient, indirect effect, and total effect from adjusting model (n=380)

Variable	R ²	Effect	Variable			
			MKINO	BLCFD	MKFOC	PDQUA
MKINO	.52	DE	-	.54*(6.71)	.46*(3.61)	.57*(6.01)
		IE	-	-	-	-
		TE	-	.54*(6.71)	.46*(3.61)	.57*(6.01)
EXPFU	.87	DE	.45*(6.83)	.49*(6.14)	-	.72*(5.62)
		IE	-	.24*(6.64)	.52*(5.35)	.14*(4.09)
		TE	.45*(6.83)	.73*(6.95)	.52*(5.35)	.86*(5.83)

$\chi^2 = 234.69$ df = 136 p-value = .00000, $\chi^2 / df = 1.72$, RMSEA = .044, RMR = .022, SRMR = .039, CFI = .99, GFI = .94, AGFI = .91, CN = 282.26

Note: Establishment of consumer confidence=BLCFD; Market focus =MKFOC; Product quality =PDQUA; Marketing innovations=MKINO; Exporters Success=EXPFU

Figure 3: Model (n=380)

Note: Establishment of consumer confidence=BLCFD; Market focus =MKFOC; Product quality =PDQUA; Marketing innovations=MKINO; Exporters Success=EXPFU

Moreover, the mediation effect of marketing innovation is addressed between establishment of consumer confidence and exporter success. The results of this hypotheses shows that marketing innovation is a mediating variable between establishment of consumer confidence and exporter success. The second mediation effect of marketing innovation is considered between market focus and exporter success. This mediation effect is also significant. Final mediation effect is considered between product innovation and export success. Academicians found that marketing innovation is a mediating variable between product quality and exporter success.

5. Discussion

This study aimed to examine the effect of establishment of consumer confidence, market focus, product quality and marketing innovation on exporter success. The exporter success of Thai furniture industry is considered. This relationship is examined with the help of mixed method approach and data analysis is carried out with the help of statistical tool. Nine hypotheses were proposed including six direct effect hypotheses and three indirect effect hypotheses.

The relationship between the establishment of consumer confidence and marketing innovation is considered in hypothesis 1. The results of this study shows that establishment of consumer confidence has positive effect on marketing innovation. The increase in the confidence among the consumers can lead to the increase in marketing innovation. As this study is based on the international consumer, therefore, international consumer is considered in the study and the confidence of international consumers on Thai furniture products is important to promote marketing innovation. Hypothesis 2 indicated the effect of the establishment of consumer confidence in relation to the exporter success. It is found that establishment of consumer confidence has positive effect on exporter success. The exporter success is based on the successful exports to various countries and successful export required the confidence of the consumer to purchase the Thai furniture products. Therefore, the increase in the development of consumer confidence can increase the exporter success. The significant relationship between export performance, marketing and consumer is consistent with the results of previous studies and the current study (Njonjo, Njeru, Kibera, & Owino, 2022). Furthermore, the relationship between market focus and marketing innovation is observed. It is observed that market focus has influential role in marketing innovation. The increase in market focus by the furniture exporting companies can increase the marketing innovation. The export companies should focus on to capture the market share to enhance the export performance. Additionally, product quality also has an influential role in the rate of success. It also has relationship with marketing innovation (Hanaysha, Abdullah, & Abd Ghani, 2014; Na, Kang, & Jeong, 2019). Hypothesis 4 indicated the effect of product quality on marketing innovation which shows that product quality has positive effect on marketing innovation. Any change in product quality can change the marketing innovation in the comparative environment which may have influence on overall performance of exports. Additionally, hypothesis 5 indicated the effect of quality on export success. The exporter success is majorly based on the quality of the products as the quality of

the products are always the requirement of the people. Literature also provides several evidences that product quality has relationship with export success (Ullah, Arslan, & Puhakka, 2021). Finally, while considering the direct effect, this study examined the effect of marketing innovation on exporter success. The hypothesis 6 identified the major relationship between marketing innovation and exporter success. The increase in marketing innovation of furniture products internationally can increase the exporter success and lead to the increase in exports volume. Similarly, previous studies also identified the positive relationship between marketing innovation and exports(Prasad, Ramamurthy, & Naidu, 2001).

Nevertheless, this study identifies the indirect effect along with the direct effect. The indirect effect of marketing innovation is considered. Hypothesis 7, hypothesis 8 and hypothesis 9 considered the indirect effect of marketing innovation. It is found that marketing innovation can transfer the positive effect of establishment of consumer confidence on exporter success. Marketing innovation can also transfer the positive effect of market focus on exporter success. Finally, product quality also has direct as well as indirect effect on exporter success through marketing innovation. According to the results of the study, marketing innovation has the potential to transfer the effect of product quality on exporter success.

6. Conclusion

It is concluded that; the connection between establishment of consumer confidence, market focus, product quality, marketing innovation and exporter success has vital importance for furniture industry. The establishment of consumer confidence, market focus, product quality and marketing innovation has the potential to promote Thai furniture industry by increasing the exporter success. The findings identified that: 1) product quality, establishment of consumer confidence, market focus, marketing innovations, and the success in the operation of Thai furniture exporters were rated at a high level; 2) product quality, establishment of consumer confidence, marketing innovations, and market focus has influence on success in the operation of the Thai furniture exporters, and 3) the model for the success in the operation of the Thai furniture exporters, developed by the current study is called QCIFS Model, consisting of Q (referring to product quality), C (referring to building consumer confidence), I (referring to marketing innovations), F (referring to market focus), and S (referring to success in the operation of Thai furniture exporters). In addition, the qualitative research findings also revealed that in creating the success in the operation of the Thai furniture exporters, the entrepreneurs should study both formal and informal customer requirements in each country, synthesize the findings, and use them to design the products to meet with the needs of the majority of customers in the countries which could be the export destinations.

6.1 Implications

The theoretical implications of the study are based on the literature gap covered by the current study. In this direction, the current study has several theoretical implications because the study considered several literature gaps. Although the furniture industry is considered by several other studies in the literature, but the current study is unique in nature having several theoretical implications. First, this study considered mixed method approach which has several

implications for the academicians. Several studies considered furniture market, however, most of the studies considered quantitative research or qualitative research, however, this study considered mixed method approach. Therefore, the study considered mixed method approach and contributed significantly to the literature. Second, number of other studies identified the factors affecting furniture industry, however, the exporter success is not considered which one of the unique elements is in the current study. Exporter success is rarely identified in the literature, but it is mentioned by the previous studies. Third, the major contribution of the study is to develop a model for exporter success. Based on the results of the study, this study proposed a model to promote exporter performance in furniture industry of Thailand. The development of this model for the furniture industry of Thailand has vital importance for the literature. Practically the implications of the current study cannot be neglected. Therefore, the results of the study have vital importance for practitioners as well as academicians to promote exporter success. The results of the study can be used to make various strategies to reestablish the furniture market. It is recommended that various factors such as consumer confidence, market focus, product innovation and marketing innovation should be considered to enhance exporter success. The research findings can be applied as the guidelines in formulating a policy to support the operation of the Thai furniture exporters. Quality of the products should be used to build consumers' confidence by utilizing marketing innovations and market focus which serve as the pull factors in the consumers' purchasing decisions. Besides, marketing competitiveness of the Thai furniture export business can also be developed through the quality of products and services.

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